

ADVANCED MOLECULAR DETECTION AND PREVALENCE OF MULTI DRUG-RESISTANCE AND EXTENSIVE DRUG RESISTANCE TUBERCULOSIS WITH GENEXPERT

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Abstract

Background: Tuberculosis is a serious global health concern with millions of cases annually and an increasing number of MDR and XDR strains. Drug-resistant TB can be diagnosed and managed quickly because of the GeneXpert system, which provides rapid and accurate molecular method for detecting MTB and drug resistance. Traditional techniques like smear microscopy and culture are time-consuming and frequently insensitive.

Objective: The present study aims to diagnose MTB using advanced molecular techniques, and identify the prevalence of MDR-TB and XDR-TB among the patient sputum specimens obtained from a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology: A total of 594 sputum samples were taken from suspected MTB patients aged between 15 and 65 years. Using MTB/RIF Ultra assay, MTB and rifampicin (RIF) resistance were initially diagnosed on GeneXpert system. The MTB-detected samples exhibiting RIF resistance were subsequently tested by MTB/XDR assay to identify resistance against various drugs used for treatment of MTB.

Result: The results exhibited the presence of MTB in 184 out of 594 samples. Of 184 such samples, 13 were found to have MDR-TB (7.1%), 4 of which were further diagnosed as XDR-TB (2.2%). Rifampicin resistance was identified in 32 cases, which were further subjected to additional drug resistance. Resistance to isoniazid was detected in 41% of these rifampicin-resistant isolates, followed by fluoroquinolone 28%, ethionamide 16%, kanamycin and amikacin each in 6%, and capreomycin in 3% of cases.

Conclusion: In conclusion, high incidence of drug-resistant tuberculosis strains, particularly the significant proportion resistant to rifampicin and isoniazid, highlights challenges in managing tuberculosis infection.

INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex (MTBC), the disease-causing organism of tuberculosis, is to date one of the most common infectious pathogens globally and today the most frequent cause of deaths attributed to a single infectious agent with an estimated 1.25 million deaths related to the infection in the year 2023. This is better than other contagious diseases like HIV, which highlights the high global health cost rating on tuberculosis (1, 2).

Tuberculosis is not a surface disease as it is transmitted through persons with it coughing, sneezing or with close contact with infected persons. It is difficult to control in low-crowd or un-ventilated areas, is easily transmitted in air by droplet nuclei, has a long incubation or latency period, and it is asymptomatic in its early stages thus making it easy to easily find its way to immunocompromised persons (3). Immune decline can reduce the effectiveness of the human body because of the poor diet and deficiencies of the nutrients that help to enhance the immunity and increase the susceptibility of the human body to tuberculosis (TB) after the ages of 10-25. (4) The primary form of disease is pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB), which is predominantly the infection spread to the lungs, but extrapulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB) is the dissemination of the infection to other body organs (5). World Health Organization (WHO) projected that 10.6 million people will have TB by 2022 (6). Reported cases of TB are alarming and have been estimated to range at 350 per 100,000 individuals annually, particularly in highly disease-endemic nations such as Pakistan (7). Pakistan is ranked fifth with an estimated 518,000 cases of TB, including 15,000 cases of MDR-TB (8). The growth of multidrug-resistant (MDR) and extensive drug-resistant (XDR) strains poses a threat to efforts in TB control and renders the current therapies ineffective, particularly in areas where TB is already widespread (9). MDR-TB is a type of tuberculosis infection caused by strains of MTB that are resistant to at least two of the most potent first-line anti-TB medications, namely isoniazid (INH) and rifampicin (RIF). Limited treatment options are necessitated by resistance

to these frontline drugs, often relying on second-line drugs, which are less potent, more toxic, and require longer treatment courses (10, 11). The MTB strain that causes XDR-TB is more resistant to any fluoroquinolone (such as levofloxacin or moxifloxacin) and at least one of the three injectable second-line medications: amikacin, capreomycin, or kanamycin. This makes XDR-TB an advanced type of MDR-TB. These resistant strains of tuberculosis are prevalent in underdeveloped nations and pose the biggest threat to affected populations and healthcare systems (10, 12).

Several studies have highlighted the problem of MDR-TB worldwide. MDR-TB and XDR-TB had overall cure rates of only 56% and 39%, respectively (13). Reported cases of TB are alarming and have been estimated to range at 350 per 100,000 individuals annually, particularly in highly disease-endemic nations such as Pakistan (7). Personalized treatment plans and periodic observing for drug resistance enhances medication treatment and reduce the transmission of tuberculosis(14, 15). The treatment of tuberculosis is prolonged, and the expenses increase when bacteriological monitoring is not performed in time (16). Molecular diagnostic techniques have revealed a substantial level of drug resistance in tuberculosis patients, which is particularly common in such areas as Bangladesh and Guyana(17, 18). A recent global meta-analysis reported that the prevalence of extensive drug-resistant XDR-TB is 2.5%, which increases to 11.6% when combined with multidrug-resistance (MDR-TB), which is alarming and indicates the necessity of better management protocols (19). In the past, researchers have reported inconsistent levels of drug resistance in the treatment of tuberculosis and particularly a high rate of MDR and XDR TB in South Asia and that predominant cases of MDR and XDR TB are reported in countries such as Pakistan, India, and China (20).

GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra and MTB/XDR assay were used to identify the MDR-TB and the XDR-TB within a short time in this research. GeneXpert is a nucleic acid amplification test

(NAAT) that is utilized to monitor *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) DNA and identify mutations pertinent to the resistance of two initially used anti-tuberculosis drugs: isoniazid and rifampicin. The GeneXpert innovation owes its success to its ability to deliver.

Quick and reliable diagnosis of MTB and drug resistance directly on patient samples, and thus reduce the time-consuming application of culture-based methods. This technology can be crucial in enhancing the fight against tuberculosis with the potential of timely screening, especially in some of the areas where the resources are limited and the commonly used drug is involved in susceptibility testing can be in practice unfeasible (21,22). GeneXpert has useful in diagnosing MTB because of a number of advantages over conventional methods. GeneXpert has been found to be rapid and therefore the diagnosis of MTB is currently favored. Detection which enables the quick instance of administering the right therapeutic regimens. In addition, GeneXpert is a highly sensitive and specific tool in the detection of drug-resistant MTB which improves epidemiological surveillance, and helps to improve patient surveillance outcomes of management and treatment. This diagnostic molecular tool comes in as a significant progress in the diagnosis and control of TB, especially in high burdensome, resource limited settings where TB is endemic. The application of this diagnostic tool offers health care professionals with a strong tool of detection of drug resistance patterns, thus, contributing to containing resistant strains of tuberculosis. The aim of the research is to determine the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) and extensive drug-resistant (XDR) MTB among suspected cases of tuberculosis that present in a tertiary care hospital. The purpose of this project is to compile necessary baseline statistics to support health authorities in developing effective responses to tuberculosis intervention strategies, based on GeneXpert diagnostic findings. The results will help in designing targeted tuberculosis control programs in Pakistan as well as other high-burden areas facing the same issues in terms of drug-resistant

tuberculosis. The widespread emergence of MDR-TB and XDR-TB has enhanced the disease to an ever more difficult stage to manage. Being a high-burden country, Pakistan lacks comprehensive data that is needed to fully understand the emergence and spread of the resistance to antibiotics across its territories. The objective of the research was to determine the number of patients who are hospitalized with MDR-TB and XDR-TB at a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan, utilizing the outcomes of GeneXpert assay

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This was a cross-sectional study that was conducted at the Molecular Diagnostic Laboratory of the Pathology Department in Allama Iqbal Medical College (AIMC) in Lahore, Pakistan. We were originally interested in establishing the prevalence of MDR-TB and XDR-TB among patients who presented to a tertiary care hospital with clinically suspected pulmonary tuberculosis. All patients signed written consent, and the protocol of this study was reviewed by the Ethical Review Board of Allama Iqbal Medical College/Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (158th meeting, dated 11 January 2024; Reference No. ERB158/14/11-01-2024/S1 ERB) and approved by the board with chairperson Prof. Farooq Ahmad Rana. The research was conducted in compliance with the guidelines and regulations of the Ethical Review Board.

Sample Size and Data Collection

A total of 594 suspected cases of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) were selected based on the previous estimates, assuming a 95% confidence range with a margin of error of 0.10 was convenient. The inclusion criteria were patients who showed to have persistent cough, fever, hemoptysis, or weight loss as symptoms of tuberculosis. Patients having known comorbidities such as HIV, taking anti-TB treatment, and those with possible co-infections were excluded from the study.

Specimen Collection and Handling

Early morning sputum samples were collected from patients according to the standard respiratory specimen collection procedures. The sputum samples were transported at 2 to 8 °C in order to preserve their integrity and prevent bacterial growth. All specimens were processed within seven days of collection to ensure viability to undertake the molecular testing.

Diagnostic Assay

We used GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra and GeneXpert MTB/XDR assays (Cepheid, USA) for molecular analysis and resistance profiling of MTB. The GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra assay is able to identify MTBC DNA and *rpoB* gene mutations, which is a sign of rifampicin resistance. It is a WHO-endorsed rapid diagnostic test that has a higher sensitivity than previous ones especially in smear-negative and pediatric MTB cases (23, 24). The GeneXpert MTB/XDR assay identifies mutations in *inhA*, *katG* (isoniazid resistance), *gyrA/gyrB* (fluoroquinolone resistance), and *eis* promoter/*rrs* genes (second-line injectable drug resistance).

Assay Procedure and Quality Control

Pre-processing: Each sputum sample was mixed in a 2:1 ratio with GeneXpert sample reagent containing isopropyl alcohol and sodium hydroxide, to liquefy the specimen and inactivate mycobacteria. The mixture was incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature.

Cartridge Loading: Two milliliters of the processed sample were transferred into a GeneXpert test cartridge, sealed, and loaded into the instrument.

Automated Detection: The GeneXpert system performed nested real-time PCR and detected drug resistance-associated mutations in a closed, contamination-free environment. Results were typically available within two hours. Each run included internal controls as recommended by the manufacturer and the entire procedure was executed under stringent internal quality control measures.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to give descriptive statistics of continuous variables like age. Frequencies and percentage were used to summarize categorical variables such as sex, drug resistance status, and TB detection. The chi-square test or Fisher exact test were used to compare categorical variables. The p-value of less than 0.05 was regarded as the statistical significance. To provide a visual representation of demographic distribution of the study population, MTB detection rates, and drug resistance patterns, bar and pie charts were used.

Results

Result 1: Demographic distribution of the study population based on gender

Among the 594 suspected MTB isolates tested in this study, majority were sampled in male patients where 351 (59.1%) of the study population was sampled, and female patients constituted 243 (40.9%) of the study population as shown in the figure below:

Fig 1: Distribution of the population used in the study in terms of gender: The pie chart shows the gender distribution of the 594 suspected cases of Mycobacterium tuberculosis. The blue segment is that of male patients, including 351 individuals (59.1%), and the orange segment is that of the female patients, including 243 people (40.9%).

Result 2: Age distribution of the study population:

Among the 594 suspected MTB isolates, most of the patients fell under the 21-45 years age group.

The average age of the population that was studied was 35 ± 1.2 years. This distribution is as shown in the table and the figure below:

Table 1: Age distribution of the study population: The table presents the number and percentage of suspected Mycobacterium tuberculosis in the various age groups with the highest prevalence being in the 21 - 45 years age group.

Age	Number of Patients	Percentage
<20	34	5.8%
21-45	398	67.0%
>45	162	27.2%

Fig 2: Age-wise distribution of the study population: The bar chart depicts that the highest suspected cases of Mycobacterium tuberculosis were in the 21 - 45 years age group (398 cases; 67.0%) and the subsequent 162 cases (27.2%) in the age group that is older than 45 years and 34 cases (5.8%) in patients under 20 years.

Result 3: Frequency of detection of MTB in the study population.

The current study involved 594 suspected MTB isolates, which were obtained in suspected patients with pulmonary tuberculosis. Of these,

184 isolates (31%) were positive for MTB and 410 (69%) were negative as summarized in the table and figure below:

Table 2: Frequency of the detection of MTB among the study population. The following table presents a summary of the detection rate of the MTB among 594 suspected pulmonary tuberculosis individuals. In 184 cases (31%), MTB was detected and in 410 (69) cases, MTB was not detected.

MTB results	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Detected	184	31%
Not detected	410	69%

Figure 3: Graphical display of the frequency of MTB detection in the study population: This pie chart shows the distribution of the detection of the MTB in the 594 suspected cases of pulmonary tuberculosis. The blue section is the 184 individuals (31%), in whom MTB was detected, while the orange segment corresponds to the 410 individuals (69%) who tested negative.

Result 4: Rifampicin-resistant cases

Rifampicin resistance was observed in 32 out of 184 cases of MTB-positive (17.4%), whereas the

remaining 152 (82.6%) cases of MTB-positive were rifampicin sensitive, as the following bar chart indicates:

Figure 4: Rifampicin resistance prevalence within cases detected by the MTB: The following bar chart represents the distribution of rifampicin resistance among 184 patients who were positive of Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB). The red bar is 32 cases of rifampicin-resistant (17.4%), whereas the blue bar is 152 cases of rifampicin-sensitive (82.6%).

Result 5: Drug resistance profile in Rifampicin resistance cases.

Among the 32 cases that were resistant to rifampicin, further drug susceptibility testing was performed through the use of MTB/XDR assay in order to determine susceptibility to other anti-tuberculosis drugs. Particularly, 13 of the 32 cases (40.6%) of the isolates resistant to rifampicin were also resistant to isoniazid, a fact that proves that the prevalence of multi drug resistant

tuberculosis (MDR-TB) is high in the considered subgroup. It was found that 9 cases (28.1%) had developed fluoroquinolone resistance and 5 cases (15.6%) developed ethionamide resistance. These isolates were found to be resistant to second-line injectable drugs in 2 cases each (6.3%) of the total resistant bacterial isolates to kanamycin and amikacin, and 1 case (3.1%) of the resistant bacterial isolates to capreomycin, as shown in the following table:

Figure 5. Drug resistance profile among Rifampicin-resistant MTB cases: This bar chart shows the distribution of resistance to six anti-tuberculosis drugs among 32 Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) cases identified as rifampicin-resistant. The most prevalent resistance was to isoniazid (13 cases, 40.6%), followed by fluoroquinolones (9 cases, 28.1%), ethionamide (5 cases, 15.6%), kanamycin (2 cases, 6.3%), amikacin (2 cases, 6.3%), and capreomycin (1 case, 3.1%).

Result 6: Prevalence of MDR-TB and XDR-TB Among MTB-positive Cases:

Among the 594 suspected MTB isolates, 184 MTB-positive cases were subjected to further testing for multidrug-resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) tuberculosis. Of

these 184 confirmed MTB cases, 13 (7.1%) were identified as MDR-TB, while 4 (2.2%) were classified as XDR-TB, as illustrated in the accompanying table and figure:

Table 3: Frequency and percentage of (MDR-TB) and (XDR-TB) cases in the study population: This table presents the frequency and percentage of MDR-TB and XDR-TB cases identified among 184 Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolates; 13 cases (7.1%) were identified as MDR-TB and 4 cases (2.2%) as XDR-TB.

	Frequency	Percentage
MTB MDR	13	7.1%
MTB XDR	4	2.2%

Figure 6: Prevalence of (MDR-TB) and (XDR-TB) in the study population: This bar chart is a horizontal bar chart that illustrates the frequency of MDR-TB and XDR-TB. Out of the 184 cases with the positive result of the MTB test, the blue bar signifies 13 (7.1%) of the MDR-TB cases and the brown bar represents 4 (2.2%) cases of the XDR-TB cases.

Discussion

World Health Organization (WHO) has approved the use of traditional drug susceptibility testing (DST) as the gold standard method, it has a long turnaround time of between 25 days to more than 2 months that can delay the treatment of patients thereby augmenting the risk of failure to treat as well as maintain the transmission of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB). Although the World Health Organization (WHO) has endorsed traditional drug susceptibility testing (DST) as the gold standard

method, its prolonged turnaround time, ranging from 25 days to over 2 months, can delay patient treatment, increasing the risk of treatment failure and continued transmission of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) (25). In TB-positive cases, early identification of MDR-TB and XDR-TB is a crucial factor in both controlling the infection and providing the patient with the best treatment(26, 27). Considering the fact that there are few effective drugs that can be used in treating tuberculosis, it is becoming harder to control the disease as the

rate of drug-resistant tuberculosis is on the increase in Bangladesh and other countries with limited resources (12).

Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) was found in the majority of the male patients (59.1%), as opposed to the female patients (40.9%), in the present study, thus gender disparity was observed and this is in tandem with national and global patterns. This is in line with different studies performed across the world and in South Asia. Previous studies, like Horton et al. (2016) and WHO (2023) statistics, show that men are more susceptible to tuberculosis (TB) than women, probably because they are more exposed to risk factors, including smoking, work-related hazards, and socialization that increase the risk of transmission (28). On the same note, a research study carried out in Pakistan by Javaid et al. (2018) established that TB is predominant in men due to differences in the social determinants and health seeking behavior (29).

The age category of 21-45 years of age was the most prevalent in terms of age distribution considering that the mean age of the population was 35 ± 1.2 years. The above observation is associated with the epidemiology of TB in the world as the disease targets young and middle-aged adults, which is the most socioeconomically active group of people. Other researches, such as those carried out by Ahmad et al. (2021) in Lahore, also indicated the same age distribution, with a focus on the public health impact due to the possible loss of productivity (30).

Out of 594 suspected patients, 184 (31%) turned out to be positive with MTB using GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra. This rate of detection is in line with other researches in the area. As an example, a positive rate was observed to be 26% with the use of GeneXpert in patients with suspected pulmonary TB in urban healthcare facilities in Pakistan (31).

GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra is a sensitive and specific diagnostic technique and a powerful first-line diagnostic instrument, particularly in the diagnosis of smear-negative and HIV-related TB. GeneXpert is recommended by the WHO as the first-line test because it has a short turnaround

time of approximately 2 hours and can also detect rifampicin resistance.

This implies that the patients were in the early or cured phases of TB or that they had other respiratory infections. It also highlights the significance of differential diagnosis and the possible need to add molecular testing to clinical examination and radiological (32).

Resistance to rifampicin was detected in 32 out of 184 MTB-positive cases (17.4%); the remaining 152 cases (82.6%) that were positive of MTB and subsequently that were sensitive to rifampicin. This prevalence is in line with the estimates of the World Health Organization according to which rifampicin-resistant or multi-drug resistant TB (MDR/RR-TB) is estimated at 3.6% of the new cases and 18% of the previously treated cases. Our findings align with the wide range of the world population, and results represented high percentages of people who were previously treated or were at risk in the study population (33).

Regionally, a study conducted in Lahore, Pakistan, using the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay has found that rifampicin resistance is found in 41.66% of cases with MTB, with an increased burden in urban tertiary care facilities. In contrast, our observed rate is lower, possibly reflecting differences in geographic coverage, patient demographics, or referral patterns (34).

Our results are further contextualized by similar data from other high-burden countries. A retrospective (7-year) study of a provincial referral TB hospital in Indonesia indicated a rifampicin resistance rate of about 14.1% in TB-confirmed cases, with a significantly higher level in previously treated patients. This comparison helps to strengthen the international issue of drug-resistant TB and the necessity of introducing molecular diagnostics to the active screening process, in particular, where the rate of retreatment is high (35).

The observed drug resistance pattern of rifampicin-resistant cases in this study partially aligns with the global prevalence of drug resistance patterns in a number of studies. The isoniazid resistance rate among rifampicin-resistant isolates was 40.6%, which, although

supportive of using rifampicin resistance as a surrogate marker of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), is notably lower than the 80-90% co-resistance rates reported in previous studies (36, 37).

The identified resistance to fluoroquinolone (28.1% of rifampicin-resistant cases) is consistent with the results reported globally, where 25-33% of MDR-TB patients have been found to be resistant to fluoroquinolone (38, 39). The resistance to ethionamide is 15.6% compared to the maximum of 22-25% in other populations, which suggests that the second-line drug resistance varies regionally and is possibly related to prior treatment regimens (40, 41).

The resistance to injectable drugs kanamycin and amikacin at 6.3% each is also on the lower end than other studies, which show a range from 5% to 15%, but still significant considering their essential use in second-line therapy. The prevalence of capreomycin resistance at 3.1% is consistent with the lower prevalence in some cohorts but indicates the growing challenge of resistance to injectable drugs of first choice (42, 43).

Out of 184 confirmed MTB-positive patients, 13 (7.1%) patients had been diagnosed with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), and 4 (2.2%) patients with extensively drug-resistant (XDR-TB). These are considerably high rates compared to WHO's global estimates, which place MDR-TB prevalence among new TB cases at ~4.2% and among previously treated patients at ~19% (WHO, 2023) (44, 45).

Our MDR-TB rate is in line with the National TB Control Program's data in their Drug Resistance Survey, which showed a 4-5% prevalence in new cases of TB. Likewise, studies from tertiary care hospitals in Punjab have reported MDR rates ranging from 5 to 7% (46).

The XDR-TB detection (2.2%) also deserves attention. In Pakistan, a multicenter study by Mahmood et al. (2020) found a prevalence of XDR-TB ranging from 1.5% to 2.5% among MDR-TB cases, especially in areas characterized by poor treatment adherence or the improper use of second-line drugs, which aligns similarly with our results. These instances are difficult due to

the unavailability of treatment options, the escalating trends of therapy failure and increased death rates. The development of XDR-TB poses a severe public health issue, as it limits therapeutic options significantly and is linked to significantly worse clinical outcomes (47).

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According to the WHO data from 2010 indicate that, 2,200 out of 7,795 registered tuberculosis retreatment cases (28%) were reported to have multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), or resistance to at least isoniazid and rifampicin—the two most effective first-line anti-TB medications. Poor detection and treatment practices are some of the factors that lead to the emergence and spread of multidrug-resistant (MDR) tuberculosis (TB) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) (4). The high drug resistance tuberculosis in Pakistan increased from 1.5% in 2006 to 4.5% in 2009

(4). As the global prevalence of drug-resistant tuberculosis (TB) cases is increasing, there is an immediate necessity of developing more rapid and reliable diagnostic technologies to provide early and appropriate treatment. This is essential to maximize patient outcomes and to make certain that the TB control programs are managed effectively (48).

The aim of the current study was to identify mutations in specific genes associated with drug resistance using the molecular diagnostic technique GeneXpert. The study also aimed to speed up the process of diagnosis. In order to reduce uncertainty and facilitate the appropriate care of those at risk of TB transmission, routine use of such quick and effective diagnostic technologies for drug-resistant TB will allow for rapid and accurate medical management. According to an analysis of 56 studies with a sample size of 350–420 participants, 2.5% of people worldwide have extensive drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB). Compared to female patients, male patients had greater rates of isoniazid-resistant TB (17.5%), rifampicin-resistant TB (12.7%), and multi-drug resistant TB (20%) (19).

In conclusion, prompt identification of MDR-TB and XDR-TB is critical for efficient patient care and prevents the spread of resistant strains. In order to address this issue, MTB is identified, and the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR-TB) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR-TB) tuberculosis is evaluated among patients at a tertiary care facility using advanced molecular diagnostics, namely the GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra and MTB/XDR assays. The early detection and containment of MDR-TB and XDR-TB cases depend on routine surveillance for TB drug resistance. The future needs should be focusing on the establishment of these sophisticated diagnostics into the regular TB care programs, as well as enhancing the surveillance systems so that they can establish efficient preventive means against MDR-TB and XDR-TB, not only in Pakistan but also in other resource-restricted countries with a heavy load of tuberculosis burden.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by **Hafiz Anas Saeed**, **Masooma Farrukh**, **Umer Farooq** and **Arslan Ullah Khan** under the supervision of **Dr. Farhan Rasheed**. The first draft of the manuscript was written by **Hafiz Anas Saeed**, and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. **Dr. Nazim Hussain** served as the corresponding author and reviewed the final version of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability

The datasets generated and analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author, **Dr. Nazim Hussain**, on reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest: No

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